

THE COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE GRAMMARS OF THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Ayxodjayeva Muborak Saidjarimovna

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ABSTRACT

The main difference between the lexicons of the Uzbek and Russian languages lies in the fact that they belong to different language families. While Uzbek is classified as an agglutinative language within the Altaic language family, it genetically belongs to the Turkic language family. As a result, the lexical richness of Uzbek and other Turkic languages is based on their unique vocabulary. In contrast, Russian is a Slavic language within the Indo-European language family, and its lexicon is primarily derived from all-Slavic and Old Russian words.

Recent statistics show that approximately 50% of words in modern Uzbek literary language are borrowed from Russian and other languages via Russian. These Russian words are used actively in both scientific and technical literature, as well as in spoken language. However, there are some differences between the original Russian words and the ones used in Uzbek, which are reflected in their phonetics. Russian words that were borrowed into Uzbek language until the beginning of the 20th century have undergone certain phonetic changes and Uzbekization, resulting in differences in pronunciation. Examples of these words include "brush," "blanket," "strawberry," "rum," and "church." These pronunciations are now considered the norm for modern Uzbek literary language. However, words that were borrowed into Uzbek relatively recently may not have undergone such changes.

This article has been significantly impacted by new research paradigms, resulting in radical changes. One of the main innovations of the article is its anthropocentric approach to linguistic phenomena, analyzing them through the lenses of Communicative and Pragmatic Linguistics, Cognitive Linguistics, Linguoculturology, and Gender Linguistics. This has led to the need for traditional notions to be reconsidered and for new terms, such as categorization and conceptualization, to be introduced. Comparative Linguistics has an interdisciplinary status, and the book is divided into six units, each containing both theoretical and practical parts.

The article covers the main notions and trends of Comparative Linguistics, its history, evaluation, different approaches, and views. It also delves into the typology of phonetic and phonological levels of English and Native languages, as well as the typology of morphological,

syntactic, and lexical levels of English and Native languages. Additionally, the book explores the interrelation of typology with anthropological trends of Modern Linguistics.

Comparative typology is a branch of linguistics that focuses on analyzing and categorizing languages based on their structural and functional characteristics. The main objective of this field is to provide a comprehensive description and explanation of the shared characteristics and structural variations among different languages around the world.

In the theoretical part of the book, fundamental problems of Comparative Linguistics are discussed, including key points for discussion, questions for self-control, recommended literature, topics for independent work for students, and a list of key-words.

The issue of determining the timeline for the history of linguistic comparison is complex and remains unresolved. The history of linguistic comparison is intertwined with the history and understanding of language, making it difficult to establish a universally accepted approach to timing this problem. We will now consider Dr. Buranov's perspective on this matter.

The third factor is the least common factor, which deals with studying unknown languages and languages that do not have a writing system. Recently, an enormous bulk of researches has been done on languages in Latin America, Asia, Africa, Australia, Oceania and Eurasia that do not have a writing system. Studying these languages have influenced by comparing them to Indo-European languages and these investigations have influenced on typology greatly. Previous researches focused on genetic relation but new researches are focusing on morphological similarities, classification, and other points.

To put it differently, there are differences in the meanings of words in Uzbek dialects compared to Russian. Some words have additional meanings in Uzbek that are not present in Russian, while some words have different meanings altogether. Ambiguity in words is common in both languages and is mostly found in the oldest lexical layers. In some cases, the meanings of words expressing the same concept are the same in both languages, but the new meanings formed from them do not correspond to each other. Therefore, it is better to compare larger units such as sentences and texts when comparing the lexicon of Russian and Uzbek languages. Uzbek language is rich in phrases, proverbs, and expressions that reflect the history, culture, traditions, and spirituality of the Uzbek people, which have been passed down through generations are considered to be units of meaning that cannot be fully understood by analyzing the meaning of each individual word, but rather by understanding the meaning of the phrase as a whole.

Despite these similarities, there are also differences in the structure and content of phrases between the Uzbek and Russian languages. For example, in Uzbek, phrases are often formed by combining a noun and an adjective, while in Russian, phrases are often formed by combining nouns or verbs. Additionally, some phrases may have different meanings or connotations in each language due to cultural or historical differences.

Overall, while phrases in both Uzbek and Russian languages are important units of meaning in speech, they differ in their structure, content, and cultural connotations.

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